

THE SPREAD OF *PARLATORIA CINEREA* HADDEN 1909, AND THE PLANTS WHICH IT PARAZITISES IN THE SOUTH OF ALBANIA

Lavdi Hasani

Department of Biology

University "Eqrem Çabej"

30 Rruga Studenti, Gjirokastër, Albania, 6000

hasanilavdi@yahoo.com

Abstract

In the following material, the role of one of the parasites of citrus fruits and ornamental plants is treated, that of *Parlatoria cinerea* Hadden 1909. Among the representatives of the U/Order Coccinea, Order Hemiptera, Class Insecta, *P. cinerea* Hadd. 1909; is presented as one of the most widespread pests among all representatives of the *Parlatoria* genus analyzed in our study. To determine this species, it is necessary to familiarize ourselves with many of its determining characteristics. It should be emphasized that, in this material, the distribution of this species in the entire territory kept under control is also dealt with. This group of parasites precisely in the Region of South-Western Albania has studied.

The paper, in addition to the spread of the species in question, also identifies the entire variety of vegetation that it frequents, the plant organs where the insect prefers to parasitize, and also the frequency of plant liking by it.

In this paper, in addition to the species *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909, data on other representatives of the genus *Parlatoria* Targi-ni-Tozzetti, 1868 are also treated, such as: *P. eleae* Colv., *P. thea* Ckll. and *P. pergandii* Comst. By presenting in a comparative manner the data collected for all these species found in the region in question, the role and importance of the study of this species is highlighted. The material also deals with data on the damage caused by it and the negative impacts on the contaminated vegetation. Thus, on the basis of a chronological work in the field of over 5 years, we have also reached a number of valuable conclusions for citrus growers and equally for park specialists who cultivate and breed ornamental plants in parks of relaxation and in the courtyards of our homes.

Keywords: *Parlatoria cinerea* Hadden 1909, plant, parasite, pygid, spread, generation, glands.

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1. Introduction

Parlatoria cinerea Hadd. is a species that belongs to a very specific group of insects that damage citrus fruits, fruit trees and ornamental plants. *Parlatoria cinerea* is a polyphagous species. It has been recorded in hosts belonging to 9 plant families. Citrus plants are their favorite "hosts". But among these "hosts" are also species of: *Annonamuricata*, *Bougainvillea*, *Citrus* spp., *Cupressus*, *Gardenia*, *Jasminum*, *Malussylvestris*, *Mangifera indica*, *Rosa*, *Viburnum* and *Vitisvinifera*, [1–3]. Our studies on U/Order Coccoinea and on this species itself are the first and only for our country.

The basic defining characteristics of this type are given concentrated in **Fig. 1, 2**.

The morphological characteristics of its waxy cover are almost similar as for the entire of the *parlatoria* genus representatives. It comes oval, convex with little height, with its apical area very acentric. Two larval integuments are usually distinguished; the first, the oldest, transparent and colorless, and the second with a very light shade of yellow. The female animal itself has a light yellow color. Its size (with the entire cover), in our samples, varies from 0.7–1.2 mm [4, 5], while from the data in [3] it can reach up to 2 mm (**Fig. 3**).

Parlatoria cinerea is a tropicopolitane species that has been described from Tahiti, but is probably not native there. Its place of origin is still uncertain. It is not present in the USA and is not well documented from Australia, New Zealand, most of Africa or and from most of Europe. It is very present in Italy and in Spain but with an incompletely known distribution. *Parlatoriacinerea* has been recorded as a citrus pest in some countries of the South Pacific region as well as in Europe [6–8]. Severe and combined infection of citrus by *P. cinerea* and *P. pergandii* is associated

with scratching, damage and cracking of the bark, causing the entire branch to dry up and sometimes killing the whole plant. *P. cinerea* causes significant damage in citrus plantations, especially in Brazil (Sao Paulo) and Argentina. The affected stages of the plants start from the stages of vegetative growth, to flowering, to fruiting and even after harvest. It has become possible for *P. cinerea* to be cultivated in the laboratory at 24 °C, 65 % relative humidity and in a light-dark regime of 12:12 hours. Thus it was discovered that, on average, egg incubation lasted 6.15 days; creep phase, 5.63 hours; first nymphal age, 6.87 days; second nymphal age 18.97 days; and each female laid up on average to 32.68 eggs [3].

Fig. 1. Body and pygidial elements in determining the type

The anal glands (in two groups) varying in number from 18-22.

Fig. 2. The view of the pygid of *P. cinerea* sketchet under binoculars; from us (above) and according to the literature (below)

Fig. 3. The view of *P.cinerea* Hadden 1909

It enters in:

- The Kingdom – Animalia;
- Type – Arthropoda;
- U/Type – Mandibulata;
- Class – Insects (Hexapoda);
- U/Class – Pterygota;
- O/Order – Hemipteroides;
- Order – Homoptera;
- U/Order – Coccoinea;
- O/Family – Paleococcoidae;
- Family – Diaspididae;
- Genus – *Parlatoria* Targini-Tozzetti, 1868;
- Species – *Parlatoria cinerea* Hadden, 1909.

2. Materials and methods

1. Determining the area of the study – South-Western Albania.
2. Setting up permanent checkpoints which were visited by us at least four times per year (at least once per season).
3. Study of the climatic conditions of the region in question [9].
4. Collecting the material in the field, storing them in test tubes in 75° alcohol and keeping relevant records.
5. Processing of the material in the laboratory until the preparation of permanent micro-preparations ready for determination. This process was carried out in the zoology laboratory near the Department of Biology of the Faculty of Science of the “EqremÇabej” University, Gjirokastra. For this, based on the methods consulted by literature [10–13], let's choose this course of ours:
 - a) insects preserved in 75° alcohol, to strip them of their the waxen cover, we take them out of there and enter them to test tubes with 8–10 % NaOH, leaving them there for about 24 hours. Then we heat them in the Mari-bath (without boiling its);
 - b) they are then taken out of the Mari-bath and rinsed in distilled water, leaving them in the water for 24 hours and changing the water several times during this time;
 - c) then the material is removed from the water and put in 70–90° alcohol, leaving it there for 10–15 minutes;
 - d) the samples are then extracted from the alcohol and placed to be colored in fuchsin solution for 24 hours (basic fuchsin);

e) fix the color by removing the material from the fuchsia and treating it with an alcohol solution that gradually increases the concentration (in 70° – 90° – 96° alcohol or absolute alcohol for 15–20 minutes for each concentration);

f) to turn the insects into permanent microscopic preparations, after they are extracted from the alcohol, they are placed in eugenol (clove oil) for 30–60 minutes and then in pure carbol-xylene solution for 15–30 minutes;

g) they are further fixed on the slide (lama), spread well on it under the binoculars, drip the Canadian balsam onto material and cover with a coverslip (lamella);

h) the preparation is then dried under the thermal effect of several electric lamps, (**Fig. 4**) and further the sides of the lamella, with the help of a fine brush, are insulated with melted paraffin;

i) these permanent micropreparations is recently passed to be observed under a binocular (microscope) for species determination according to the keys given in literaturs [14–22]. For this let's rely on the variety of glands, spines, hairs, anal ring, plates, densoria, apophyses, combs, etc. as well as their topography.

Fig. 4. The mechanism built with electric lamps for drying micropreparations

3. Results and discussion

For a period of over 5 years, we have regularly collected material for each season at each of the checkpoints seen on **Fig. 5**. Based on this, we have not met this species at all our points of control. It has been met in only 7 of our checkpoints such as: Orikum and Sevaster [Vlora], Memaliaj and Beçisht [Tepelenë], Pandelejmon and Komat [Saranda] and “AsimZeneli” [Gjiro-kastër], (**Fig. 6**).

Fig. 5. Checkpoints set up and controlled by us in the region under study

After preparing the permanent micropreparations, observing them under bin-oculars, we carried out the determination of the type. During this process we also made a series of sketches and photographs of the identifying elements of the species, (**Fig. 2, 7**).

Fig. 6. Site-gatherings of the material under study

Fig. 7. Under binocular view of micropreparations prepared by us: *a* – pygidial parts and anal ring; *b* – glands around the anal ring; *c* – the patties and the combs; *d* – full view of the specie

The size of the species (with a waxen cover), as we have mentioned above, while in our samples it reaches up to 1.2 mm, in the data of [3] it is cited that it reaches up to 2 mm. The material collected and analyzed, during this period, mainly belongs to the months of December, January, February, March, and May, always for two consecutive years (one by one). This sheet for the presence of the two basic stages in their biological cycle, that of wintering, as adults with cover and eggs deposited under it – December, January, February – as well as for imago of the next stage when the eggs begin to hatch with the arrival of spring – March, April, May. These insects give several generations a year; mainly up to three generations. We have presented this in the table through the axes of the annual cycle, (Table 1).

Table 1

Periods of collection of imago individuals (wintering adults and adults that hatch eggs) [+] and periods of their non-collection as a result of their mobile larvae (as first and second instar larvae) [-]

No.	The months of years in studies during which the species in question was encountered	Shapes met	The collection	Species name (<i>Parlatoria cinerea</i> Hadden 1909)		
				The stages of its life cycle		
				The axis of the annual cycle. Generation I	The axis of the annual cycle. Generation II	The axis of the annual cycle. Generation III
1	March		+			
2	April		+			
3	May		+			
4	June		-			
5	July		-			
6	August		-			
7	September		-			
8	October		-			
9	November		-			
10	December		+			
11	January		+			
12	February		+			

Note: – Imago with eggs (orange); – Imago with hatching eggs (green); – Larval stage I (yellow); – Larval stage II (blue)

The territories where the vegetation found to be contaminated by this parasite is located are located at altitudes from 10 m above sea level to 400 m above sea level, (Fig. 8). In terms of the climatic zones of the region, living things are found starting from the coastal climatic zones to the deep (continental) climatic zones, from the lowland Mediterranean climatic zone to the hilly Mediterranean climatic zone to the pre-mountainous one. The most favorable for *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909 is the coastal climatic zone.

= Months when the species has not been encountered

- Series 1 = Minimum height values by month
- Series 2 = Average I height values by month
- Series 3 = Average II height values by month
- Series 4 = Maximum height values by month

Fig. 8. Spread of this species in height above sea level

From the genus *Parlatoria*, associated with the species in question, we also found *P. oleae* Colv. (Orikum, Vlorë; Delvinë; Tepelënë, Beçisht;), *P. pergandii* Comst. (Saranda, city) and *P. thea* Ckll. (Vlora, city). Thus, from the genus *Parlatoria*, in our research region, we have identified only four species: *P. cinerea* Hadde., *P. oleae* Colv., *P. thea* Ckll. and *P. pergandii* Comst. (**Table 2**).

From our side, *P. cinerea* Hadde has been found in these types of plants: plum, laurel, almond, olive, peach, apple, rose and pear, [23, 24]; (**Table 2**); (**Fig. 10**). In the field, we found not few plants almost completely degraded by the presence of parasites of this group of insects.

Plant organs contaminated by *P. cinerea* Hadde are presented as follows: in Plum (*s*), in Laurel (*l*), in Almond (*s*), in Olive (*s, l*), in Peach (*s*), in Apple (*s*), in Trendafil (*s*) and in Pear (*s*). [Vo: (*s*)=stem, (*l*)=leaf]. The tangibility of plant species from each of the species of the genus *Parlatoria* is given in **Table 2**.

Table 2

Vegetation contaminated by each species of the genus *Parlatoria*

No. Ordinal	The variety of plants frequented by them	The name of the parasite			
		<i>P. cinerea</i> Hadde	<i>P. oleae</i> Colv.	<i>P. thea</i> Ckll.	<i>P. pergandii</i> Comst.
1	Plum	+	+	-	-
2	Laurel	+	+	-	-
3	Almond	+	+	-	-
4	Olive	+	-	-	-
5	Peach	+	-	-	-
6	Apple	+	-	-	-
7	Rose	+	+	-	-
8	Pear	+	+	-	-
9	Nespull	-	+	+	-
10	Persimmo	-	+	-	-
11	Orange	-	-	-	+
12	Tangarine	-	-	-	+

How the frequency of touching different plants from each of the species of this genus is presented. This is best represented in **Fig. 9**.

The occurrence in percentage of *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909 in each of the contaminated plants

Fig. 9. The ratio in percentage of different plants affected by each species

While the frequency of touching, only by *P. cinerea*, on different types of plants is reflected in **Fig. 10**.

If to analyze in which plant organs this species prefers to be placed, it is possible to see that the stem prevails in relation to the leaf, **Fig. 11**.

Fig. 10. Percentage of vulnerability of each plant

Fig. 11. The percentage of vulnerability of each plant organ

So it is possible to take into consideration that:

1. The presence of *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909 also in our country requires that this fact should be taken into consideration by growers and breeders of all types of these plant groups.
2. It should be kept in mind that this species also affects a number of decorative plants.
3. The period of treatment of vegetation with chemical disinfectants, for the region in question, should start there from April-May until the end of August (**Table 1**).

4. Conclusions

Based on the **Fig. 5, 6**, it is immediately noticeable that *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909 was not found in all our checkpoints. It extends its habitat from the coastal Mediterranean climatic zone to the Mediterranean pre-mountain one; in height from 10 m above sea level to a height of 400 m above this level, (**Fig. 8**).

The animal, in our samples (together with the waxen cover) reaches a size of 1.2 mm, from 2 mm according to [3].

In the **Table 1**, it is clear that the collection of material is favored by the wintering imago forms (December, January, February), as well as by the wintering imago that begin to hatch their eggs (March, April, May). In the other stages it becomes difficult to collect them due to the impossibility of observation with free sight.

In our case we have ascertained three generations, they replace one by one each other (**Table 1**).

Based in **Table 2** it is possible to see that the range of “host” plants of this species, in relation to others, is greater.

We have plants where this parasitic species it has been found only by foreign authors [3], or the opposite even only by us, (**Table 2**).

Among the species of the genus *Parlatoria*, found in the region studied by us, we note that the widest range of infection of the plant varieties is possessed by particularly this species, (**Table 2, Fig. 9**).

Is confirmed by our results that Infections in the bark are mainly from *P. cinerea* (94 % of all infections and in over 60 % of those in the stalk). But this species, in the region in question, has a wider association with the other specie *P. oleae* Colv. which therefore, in this region, comes second (after it) in terms of the range of plant species infected by it (**Table 2, Fig. 9**).

Among the plant species contaminated by *P. cinerea* Hadden 1909, in our case, the first place is occupied by apple with 25 % of cases, almond and olive with 17 % of cases, plum with 9 % of cases and with other queues, (**Fig. 10**). This also speaks of the polyphagia of this species.

Regarding the preferred plant organ to settle (this parasite), unlike many other species, it appears that it prefers the stem of the plant, especially its cavities and young buds, (**Fig. 11**). As can be seen in this graph, in 77 % of cases it was found to be located on the stems of plants.

This species also represents a parasite with a wide spectrum of parasitism as it is found in many types of plant groups. We find it in citrus fruits, fruit trees and also in decorative plants, (**Table 2, Fig. 10**).

Our identification of the species in question, as a pest in plum culture, is also supported by other researchers in the country [23–25].

The absence of this species in other parts of this region (especially when it is found in parts close to them in this region), may have to do not only with its real non-spreading in these areas but also with the probability of cases in search or even with the massiveness and diversity of the vegetation in them.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Manuscript has data included as electronic supplementary material (Lit. 3 and 25).

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